

THE ESSENCE OF THE KHANAFI SCHOOL AND ITS HISTORICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Qosimov K.I.

Teacher at the Department of Social Sciences, Fergana Medical Institute of Public Health

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14580736>

Abstract. *This article attempts to elucidate the life of Abu Hanifa, the founder of one of the Islamic sects, Hanafi, and to clarify the essence of the Hanafi school of thought along with its primary socio-historical characteristics.*

Keywords: *Hanafi, jurisprudence, school of thought, beliefs, theology, preferred actions, companions, successors.*

Introduction. It is well-known that the majority of Islamic beliefs in our country are practiced based on the Hanafi school. Specifically, this school distinguishes itself among the four Sunni jurisprudential schools due to its numerous adherents over the centuries, solid foundations, and accessibility. Consequently, the widespread adoption of this doctrine among various peoples in numerous countries can be attributed to the fact that the ideas it promotes align with the essence of Islam, calling all believers towards righteousness, goodness, and humanity. Therefore, the Development Strategy of our country sets the goal of "In-depth study and wide dissemination of the rich scientific heritage of our great ancestors" [1] (73). We believe that the study of this topic will be of great importance for improving the teaching of religious studies, which was introduced as a compulsory subject in all higher educational institutions of our country this year. Therefore, the scientific study of this topic and the understanding of its historical significance remains an urgent task.

Analysis of literature related to the topic. Nowadays, many scientific studies have been conducted on the issue of the Hanafi sect, its founder, its introduction and dissemination in our country. In specific sources:

- In addition to scientific research regularly published by the Muslim Board of Uzbekistan, Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf, scholars of the International Academy of Islam Muhammad Ayub Gamidov, Obid Mirkhamidov, Abdulaziz Usmanov, Akmal Mirkhamidov and the son of Salahiddin Abdughaffar ("Imam Azam" T. Semurg, media publication 2018) conducted scientific research;

- Ismailov Akramkhan - the idea of the emergence of the Hanafi school [2] (The emergence of the Hanafi school - Hidayat);

- Ekhson Shenojak - writes about the life and work of Imam Abu Hanifa, including his ability to find a solution to any problem [3] (based on the materials of Imam Azam. Tashkent - 2023);

- In the Islamic reference book - the unique side of Abu Hanifa (May Allah bless Him and grant Him peace) in the matter of ijtiḥad is emphasized, unlike other sects, he widely used comparison and istehsan [4] (Islamic reference book - Tashkent. Gafur Gulam Publishing House. 2022). 98 p.);

- The son of Soatmurad Orol, he drew the historical trends of the spread of the Hanafi school [6] (Spread of the Hanafi school / file:///C:/Hanafi...Hidayat.uz.html).

It seems that this topic has always interested everyone. Therefore, a deeper study and generalization of this topic comes from the requirements of the science of religion, which is included as a compulsory study in higher education institutions.

Research methodology. In the process of research, comparative analysis, historicity and logic, creativity, methods of system analysis were used.

Analysis and results. It is known that schools of jurisprudence were formed during the time of associates and subordinates. These schools are not named after a specific person, but after the inhabitants of the city and region. For example, the Madinah Madhhab, the Makkan Madhhab, etc. In turn, the inhabitants of the city or region followed the fatwas of local scholars. Naturally, there were subtle differences between the sect of the inhabitants of one city and the sect of the inhabitants of another city. The reason for this is that not all the companions who issued the fatwa were equally knowledgeable about the hadiths spoken by the Prophet. Moreover, their scholarly capabilities and directions of ijthihad were not the same.

It can be seen that the Hanafi sect was not formed solely on the basis of the ijthihad of Imam Abu Hanifa. Abu Hanifa, may God bless him and grant him peace, is a prominent representative of the Iraqi school of jurisprudence. The foundations of the Iraqi school of jurisprudence are based on Hazrat Ali, may God bless him and grant him peace, Abdullah bin Masood, may God bless him, and more than one and a half thousand companions who lived in Kufa.

Although, the Hanafi sect emerged in the juts of Imam Abu Hanifa in Kufa. As we have already mentioned earlier, the city of Kufa was a major scientific center [2]. The founder of the Hanafi school is Abu Hanifa, that is, Imam Azam. His real name was an-Nu'man ibn Thabit ibn Zuto, his pen name was Abu Hanifa, and his title was Imami Azam (the Great Imam). Of Persian origin, he lived in 699-767 and was a lawyer and scholar who introduced the use of the most acceptable and useful conclusions for Muslims based on sources (i.e. the principle of istihsan), the application of local legal norms. norms that comply with the Sharia. At the same time, he was a man of keen intellect, deep insight, common sense and determination to find convincing evidence compared to those who had an unparalleled genius for making new judgments based on evidence.

Abu Hanifa's grandfather was named Zuto, he was from Kabul, and also lived for some time in the cities of Termez, Naso, Anbar and Babylon. After the Arabs conquered Kabul, Zuto was taken prisoner by them, and after accepting Islam (during the caliphate of Hazrat Umar, may Allah be pleased with him), he was released from captivity. Thus, he went to Kufa, one of the newly founded major cities of the Muslim world at that time, and settled and lived there. According to sources: "His grandfather is Kabul. ... Later he went to Kufa, where he met Hazrat Ali, may Allah be pleased with him, and prayed for his descendants ... [3.4b]." Zuto gives birth to a child named Sobit in Kofe. Sobit is the father of Abu Hanifa.

Abu Hanifa grew up in a respectable, wealthy, pious Muslim family in Kufa. He was the only child of his parents. His father was a tailor and sold clothes, cloth and other fabrics in his famous shop in Kufa. Abu Hanifa also continued his father's business. He learned the Holy Quran very early.

The Imam, born in Kufa, spent most of his life in this city. At first, his father's profession was related to commerce. He was an extremely reliable person in business, did not deceive anyone and due to this, in a short period of time, he enjoyed great respect from all the weavers in the silk market.

The Imam, who learned that his trading partner sold a customer unnecessary fabric without informing him of the fault, was displeased with this, and added money for other things to the money for the sold fabric and sent it as alms. The value of the common property was 30 dirhams, which was considered a huge amount at that time. Then they no longer did business with those partners who acted carelessly. Over time, this man's business expanded, he had his own silk-spinning enterprise, which employed many workers.

Abu Hanifa traded in a store with his father until he met Shaabi, a great scholar of that time. Meeting Shaabi was a prelude to great goodness and kindness in the life of Abu Hanifa.

Abu Hanifa, may God bless him and grant him peace, recalled this: "One day I passed in front of Shaabi." He was sitting. They called me before them and asked: "Who do you study with?" they asked. ... I said: "I take fewer lessons from the scholars." He said: "Don't do this, you are obliged to study and sit with the scholars." Because I sense alertness and vigilance in you." Then my heart was touched by the words of Shaabi, I left my craft and began to study. As a result, God interested me in His words [3.37p].

"When Abu Hanifa, may God bless him and grant him peace, entered education, he decided to study all the sciences and began to receive a systematic education in various fields. At first, he studied one of the important sciences "Nahw" (Arabic linguistic science, in particular its part that studies the composition of words and sentences, i.e., the grammar of the Arabic language). Having learned it perfectly, he began to study the science of logic.

In those years, the city of Kufa was one of the major cultural centers of Muslims, where more than a hundred, and according to some sources, more than one and a half thousand subjects and subjects lived. They were happy to share their knowledge with their students. In the mosques of Kufa, there were three circles of knowledge:

1. Meetings of Kalam, where religious issues are discussed.
2. Hadith collections based on Hadith and related sciences.
3. Jurisprudence rings that teach the methods of giving rulings and fatwas based on the Quran and Sunnah.

There were many debates and arguments on religious issues in these mosques and Abu Hanifa would not join them and would begin to study the knowledge of the Word in earnest. To achieve this goal, he would travel to the city of Basra many times and finally stay there for a year. As time went on, this man's knowledge increased, his horizons broadened and his level of thinking increased. In Basra, he would argue and debate with the misguided sects, the mulhids (disbelievers in God) and various types of misguided people to ward off the harm they wanted to do to the Shari'ah. He would hasten their minds by providing convincing documents and evidence against them. They would argue with the mulhids until they understood the Shari'ah. Sometimes the apostles and the Shiites who had gone into gulul also participated in these disputes. He will also prove them with sufficient, clear and convincing evidence.

Over time, Abu Hanifa's interest in jurisprudence grew. Therefore, he abandoned teaching in word circles and began to attend meetings on jurisprudence, in particular, the lessons of the "great jurist - Hammad ibn Abu Sulayman", according to his own words. He loved his teacher so much that he listened attentively to everything he said and remembered it.

Imam Azam attended the classes of Hammad ibn Abu Sulayman for 18 years – he was his assistant in all respects until his teacher passed away. When Hammad was out of town, Abu Hanifa taught him and answered his questions. Once, when his teacher was out of Kufa for two months,

Abu Hanifa was asked about things that he had not heard from his teacher. The Imam did not lose himself and found a unique solution to each problem, relying on his mind, intellect and power of thought. Upon returning from the trip, his teacher showed him the answers he had written down to about sixty questions. Hammad approves of forty of these fatwas and opposes twenty of them.

Nevertheless, Abu Hanifa did not stop learning. He visited the cities of Mecca, Basra, Hijaz, learned from many scholars living there and served them. He made his first pilgrimage with his father at the age of 16, and later, it is said, he visited the Holy Kaaba almost 50 times during his life. At that time, many companions and subordinates formed their circles of knowledge around the Kaaba. Abu Hanifa, as a direct participant in these circles, received unprecedented knowledge from them.

In the year 120 AH, when the Ustads died, the Iraqis were looking for a successor who could take his place. The people of Kufa thought that Hammad's son Ismail was worthy of his place, but Ismail's interest in poetry and Arabic history prevailed over jurisprudence and could not justify this task. After this, Musa ibn Kathir sat on Hammad's chair. Later it will be known that Musa also lacked the ability for jurisprudence. As soon as Musa left for Hajj, the people of Kufa approved the candidacy of Abu Hanifa for the chair of knowledge. The seekers of knowledge attend Abu Hanifa's lectures and realize that his gatherings contain a wide range of knowledge, and do not attend other gatherings of knowledge. Day by day, his knowledge and wisdom became clearer: his lessons began to motivate not only students but also scholars.

When Imam Azam was sitting in Masjid al-Haram during the Hajj season, many great jurists gathered from the West and the East would approach him on many issues that were troubling them. The Imam would issue a fatwa to them – when the issue was resolved, “Allahi Akbar!” he would shout. Once, someone asked: “How did you find a solution to this problem that even the companions were thinking about?” Imami Azam responded to the objection of his tribe thus: “Do you think that I have reached this point by chance? I have pondered over this important issue for twenty years, collected all the necessary information and rulings, and examined the opinions of each companion one by one. As a result, I have arrived at this solution [3.56].”

By this time, Abu Hanifa's fame and voice had spread to the surrounding cities and the entire world. "Now the only scholar in the world is Abu Hanifa!" Indeed, his decisions and judgments on various complex issues attracted many people with their extraordinary reliability, reasonableness and popular patriotism.

In general, Abu Hanifa (May Allah bless Him and grant Him peace) had his own methods of ijtiḥād. He himself said about this: “I take my judgments from the Quran.” If I cannot find it in the Quran, I will find it in the Sunnah of the Messenger of Allah, may Allah bless him and grant him peace. If I do not find it among them, I will look for it among the Companions... As for the subordinates... I have the right to perform ijtiḥād like them.” - says [3.68]. In addition, it is stipulated there that the hadith must be popular among reliable people, scholars, and that the narrator must not follow the hadith that he narrated. It is narrated that Abu Hanifa (May Allah bless Him and grant Him peace) once, in order to check the authenticity of the hadith, approached the scholar who narrated it in order to hear it from his own lips. Imam Azam witnessed the following scene: in order to drive his sheep into the pen, the narrator was making false gestures to encourage the sheep to follow him, pretending that there was food in them with his dry hands. Upon seeing this situation, he turned away, disappointed with the narrator.

It should also be noted that the unique feature of Abu Hanifa (May Allah bless Him and grant Him peace) in the matter of ijtihad is that, unlike other madhhabs, he made extensive use of comparisons and analogies. “Istehsan” (Arabic: “confirmation”, “approval”) is the act of choosing the most convenient and useful for the Muslim community from the conclusions that can be obtained from the comparative application of Sharia issues [4.98b]. In fact, Abu Hanifa was the first to apply this practice in Sharia. Particular attention in his work is paid to local traditions and values. That is why, due to these specific features of the Imami Azam sect, it soon became popular in many Muslim countries, and the number of its followers increased more and more.

Abu Hanifa (May Allah bless Him and grant Him peace) was the first jurist to present fatwa on hypothetical issues. He further expanded the field of jurisprudence by predicting the solution of issues that had not yet arisen. Sources mention about sixty thousand of his fatwas and rulings on these “fatal issues” that may occur. In total, Imam Azam (May Allah bless Him and grant Him peace) found solutions to five hundred thousand problems in the field of jurisprudence during his life.

Imam Abu Hanifa (may God bless him and grant him peace) spent 52 years of his life under the Ummawi rule and 18 years under the Abbasid state. He witnessed two Islamic states. However, both of them oppressed Imam Azam, that is, the suffering inflicted on him was carried out during two reigns. The first of these was during the time of Ibn Hubayra, the governor of the Umawi state in Iraq, Marwan ibn Muhammad, and the second was during the Abbasid period.

Ibn Hubayra wanted to use the scholars to protect the Umawi state from harm. So he sent a message to Abu Hanifa along with some jurists from Iraq. His intention was to recruit these scholars into the service of the state administration and to appoint Abu Hanifa as a judge in the province of Kufa. Abu Hanifa, who always stands for truth and justice, naturally refuses this assignment. In his opinion, state officials never follow the rules of Sharia: "He (the mayor) wants to write a death sentence for someone who wants to behead me, and I approve of this, right?" By God, I will never take on such a responsibility [5].

Hubayra imprisons Abu Hanifa. On his orders, the executioner in prison humiliated him with ten lashes every day. On the tenth day of his imprisonment, he was brought to the governor again. Upon hearing his proposal being refused, the governor ordered him to be given another twenty lashes on the head.

When the Great Imam woke up in the morning, his face and eyes were swollen from the blows. Impressed by his determination, Hubaira released Imam Azam from custody.

Abu Hanifa on this trip went straight to the city of Mecca, where he lived until the establishment of the Abbasid state.

Abu Hanifa welcomed the establishment of the Abbasid state with impatience and excitement. He thought that all the torture inflicted on him had ended. However, the Imam could not remain silent in the face of the injustice of the dictatorial regime towards the common people; he demanded truth and justice, even if he put his life in danger. When the people of Mosul rebelled against the Caliph Mansur, Abu Hanifa sided with the rebellious people and defended them. Even in his classrooms, he did not hesitate to publicly criticize the political system and its injustices. Mansur's spies followed him everywhere and reported every word he said. However, the political establishment did not want to publicly punish him. Because by this time, Abu Hanifa's reputation among the people had grown so much - he had become a judge not only in Kufa, but in the entire Muslim world. His name was mentioned favorably everywhere.

The establishment of the city of Baghdad was a good opportunity for the political system. Caliph Mansur offered Abu Hanifa a new position as a city judge. When he refused, he was arrested. By order of the Caliph, he was taken to the marketplace for ten days and beaten ten times a day in front of the people. Each time he refused, Abu Hanifa was imprisoned for an indefinite period. It is not known how long he remained in prison, but reliable information indicates that when Abu Hanifa felt that the moment of his death was near, he fell into a prostration and died while prostrating.

He was from the unconquered pure lands in the east of Baghdad, and he was bequeathed to be buried in the cemetery of Khayzuran. By this, Imam Azam made it clear that his body would not remain in the lands of the oppressors.

According to sources, about fifty thousand people gathered for his funeral. The funeral prayer was performed six times, the last one was performed by his own son Hammad. Due to heavy traffic, the funeral will take place in the afternoon. Funeral services were held at his grave for twenty days.

If we look at history, we know that Abu Mansur Moturidi developed the religious views of Abu Hanifa and contributed to the strengthening of the Hanafis in Movarunnahr as the Moturidi sect.

Movarunnahr-Hanafiism spread widely throughout the adjacent territory - Khorasan, East Turkestan, the Caucasus and Kazan. After the Mongol invasion (first quarter of the 13th century), the lawyers of these countries were scattered everywhere. Most of them gathered in the cities under the control of the Ottoman state - the land of Rum. Jurisprudence, which was dying out as a result of the conquest, received new development. The extent to which the Hanafi madhhab was developed can be found out by the location of 92 fatwa books on the territory of the Ottoman Empire. The judges and sheikhs of the Ottoman state were appointed only from among the Hanafis. It should be said that Hanafiism spread to the territory of the Ottoman Empire through Movarunnahr, and the Hanafis in this region studied the Baghdad school through Movarunnahr [6].

It is also worth noting that a great contribution to the development of Hanafiism in India was made by Hanafi scholars who went with the Baburis from Movarunnahr. Through the Ottomans, Hanafiism also spread to Sindh (Pakistan). Shah Waliullah Dehlavi was the bearer of the development of the Hanafi school in India and Sindh. Hanafi jurisprudence developed here along with the study of hadith and interpretation.

These days, the majority of the peoples of Turkey, the Balkans, Bulgaria, Bosnia, Greece, Yugoslavia, Albania, Ukraine, the Caucasus, Kazan, Ufa, the Urals, Siberia, Central Asia, China, Manchuria, Japan, Afghanistan, Baluchistan, Siam, India, Kashmir, Pakistan, belong to the Hanafi sect. More Hanafis live in Crimea, Azerbaijan, Dagestan, fewer in Yemen, Aden, Hijaz, Egypt and Palestine, and even fewer in Syria and Tunisia.

Summary and recommendations. Thus: - The history of the penetration of the Hanafi sect into our country is associated with Abu Hafs Kabir, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, who lived in 150-217 AH;

- That man learned the Hanafi madhhab from Imam Muhammad, may God bless him and grant him peace, and, having come to Bukhara, taught according to this madhhab;

- As a result, this jurisprudence became the official sect of worship in our country.

Together with them: - A great contribution to the development of the Hanafi sect in Central Asia was made by scholars of our country, including Muhammad ibn Ismail al-Bukhari, Ibn Isa al-Tirmidhi, Burhaniddin Margilani;

- In particular, in Samarkand in 1178, the work of Burhaniddin Margilani "Al-Hidaya" was written, which became the main guide of the Hanafi school of law in the entire Islamic world. It should be noted here that the Hidayah is based on the works of Abu Hanifa and Numan ibn Thabit, one of the founders of fiqh science, and other fiqh scholars. It consists of four juz's and was used as the main guide to Muslim jurisprudence for many centuries in many Muslim countries, especially in Central Asia, until the 1930s.

Based on the information above, we recommend that the essence of this Hanafi school be included as a separate topic in the religious studies program, that is, to deepen its study in the process of educating future youth.

REFERENCES

1. PF-60 dated 01/28/2022. On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026
2. Ismailov Akramkhan. file:/The emergence of the Hanafi sect – Hidayah
3. Ehsan Shenojak. In the footsteps of Imam Azam. Tashkent - 2023
4. Islamic link. Tashkent. Gafur Ghulam Publishing House. 2022, 98 p.
5. Ehsan Shenojak. In the footsteps of Imam Azam. Tashkent - 2023. 23 p.
6. Son of Soatmurad Orol. Spread of the Hanafi sect/file:///C:/Hanafi...Hidayat.uz.html
7. "Imomi Azam" - T.: "Semurg Media", 2018.